

Reaction of varieties and selections to green leafhopper (GLH) and tungro (RTV) in the greenhouse

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We evaluated selected varieties and lines for resistance to GLH and RTV.

Six-day-old seedlings were infested with 4 second- and third-instar GLH nymphs/ seedling, using the no-choice seedling bulk test. Damage was rated at 7 d after inoculation, when susceptible check TN1 died. The experiment was repeated 3 times with 8 replications of 15 seedlings/variety.

For RTV inoculation, ten 2-wk-old seedlings of each variety were separately exposed for 24 h to 2 adult GLH which had 2-d acquisition feeding on RTV-infected TN1 plants. Infected plants were counted 14 d after inoculation.

Varieties and selections were categorized as 1) resistant to both insect and virus, 2) resistant to insect but susceptible to virus, 3) susceptible to insect but resistant to virus, and 4) susceptible to both insect and virus (see table).□

Reaction of selected varieties and lines to GLH and RTV. IRRI, 1986.

Variety	GLH rating	RTV (%)
<i>Resistant to GLH and RTV</i>		
Pankhari 203	3	0
IR29725-109-1-2-1	3	30
IR32307-107-3-2-2	3	30
IR32429-47-3-2-2	3	30
IR32453-20-3-2-2	3	20
IR33043-46-1-3	3	20
<i>Resistant to GLH, susceptible to RTV</i>		
Ptb 18	1	70
ASD7	1	90
Palasithari 601	3	90
IR28222-9-2-2-2	3	100
IR28224-3-2-3-2	1	70
IR28228-199-2-3-1-1	3	70
<i>Susceptible to GLH, resistant to RTV</i>		
Utri Rajapan	9	0
Utri Merah	7	0
ARC11554	7	10
Naria Bachi	9	30
ARC10342	7	50
Basmati	7	60
<i>Susceptible to GLH and RTV</i>		
ARC10980	7	70
IR22	7	100
IR42	7	80
TN1	9	100

Ragged stunt virus (RSV) concentration in tolerant rice

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Seven-day-old seedlings of Sitopas, Ptb 18, Tetep, and Lemo, which have symptomatic resistance (tolerance) to RSV, and several nontolerant varieties were individually inoculated with RSV and transplanted in pots. Uninoculated seedlings were transplanted as a check. Five RSV-infected and 3 uninoculated plants of each variety were individually tested for height and RSV concentration at 30 and 45 d after infection (DI).

Whole plants except roots were separately homogenized with buffer solution and the sap at 1/5 dilution was directly tested in ELISA. For ELISA, Micro ELISA Plate (Dynatech) was coated with immunoglobulin to RSV at

2 µg/ml and immunoglobulin-alkaline phosphatase conjugate was diluted 300 times. RSV concentration in sap was indicated by absorbance value at 405 nm. In ELISA, absorbance of uninfected plant sap was below 0.05 throughout the tests.

Infected seedlings of all varieties showed typical RSV symptoms. Plant height reduction at 30 DI was high in RSV-infected plants of all varieties (see table). At 45 DI, height reduction was less in Sitopas, Lemo, and TN1. RSV concentration in Sitopas and Ptb 18 was consistently lower than in other varieties. Although RSV concentration was generally lower in tolerant varieties than in nontolerant varieties at 45 DI, the difference was not significantly large. Resistance to RSV in the varieties tested may not be due solely to their resistance to RSV multiplication.□

Plant height reduction and RSV concentration at 30 and 45 DI in plants of 10 rice varieties infected at 7 d after soaking. IRRI, 1985.

Variety	RSV concentration ^a		Height reduction (%)	
	30 DI	45 DI	30 DI	45 DI
Sitopas	0.86 ± 0.19	0.84 ± 0.01	34	2
Ptb 18	0.89 ± 0.09	0.87 ± 0.00	33	15
Tetep	1.13 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.09	35	16
Lemo	1.00 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.20	28	0
Ptb 21	0.94 ± 0.00	1.10 ± 0.13	24	11
Utri Rajapan	0.93 ± 0.08	1.01 ± 0.10	21	11
Khao Mali	1.06 ± 0.01	1.06 ± 0.01	21	8
Khao-Tah-Haeng	1.07 ± 0.17	1.20 ± 0.19	28	46
Kirikara	1.15 ± 0.06	1.10 ± 0.13	26	16
TN1	1.24 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.09	26	4

^aIndicated by absorbance at 405 nm of sap at 1/5 dilution in ELISA.

Symptoms and yield reduction in tolerant varieties infected with ragged stunt virus (RSV)

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Seedlings of 10 selected varieties were transplanted 7 d after soaking (DAS), in 16- × 16- × 19-cm pots with fertile soil at 3 seedlings/pot. Seedlings were inoculated at 7, 15, 30, 45, and 60 DAS. Uninoculated plants served as control. Trials were established Sep 1984 and Nov 1985, with three replications each.

Plant height, major symptoms, and grain yield were noted for each plant. Seedlings inoculated at 7 and 15 DAS developed symptoms characteristic of RSV about 2 wk after inoculation. Emergence of new leaves was delayed and leaves were short, ragged or twisted, and darker in color. At 1 mo after inoculation, newly developed leaves were less abnormal in all varieties. At 2 mo after inoculation, many varieties showed vein swelling and occasional ragged or twisted leaves, but less stunting (Table 1). The symptoms were especially milder in Sitopas, Ptb 18, and

Table 1. Symptoms^a and plant height reduction at 30 and 60 d after infection in 10 rice varieties infected with RSV 7 d after soaking, Sep 1984, IRRI.

Variety	30 d after infection		60 d after infection	
	Symptoms	Height reduction (%)	Symptoms	Height reduction (%)
Sitopas	R ⁺⁺⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	24	Tw, V	7
Ptb 18	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	29	R ⁺ , V ⁺⁺	17
Tetep	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	29	R ⁺⁺ , V ⁺	22
Lemo	R ⁺ , Tw	57	R ⁺⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	36
Ptb 21	R ⁺ , Tw	59	V ⁺⁺	20
Utri Rajapan	R ⁺	52	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	21
Khao Mali	Tw	43	V ⁺⁺	21
Khao-Tah-Haeng	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	45	R ⁺⁺ , V ⁺	43
Kirikara	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	68	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺⁺	34
TN1	R ⁺ , V ⁺	56	R ⁺⁺ , Tw, V ⁺⁺	25

^aR = ragged leaves, Tw = twisted leaves, V = vein swelling. +, ++, +++ = degree of severity from low to high.

Table 2. Yield reduction in 10 rice varieties infected with RSV at different days after soaking, IRRI, Sep 1984.

Variety	Yield reduction (%)				
	7 DAS	15 DAS	30 DAS	45 DAS	60 DAS
Sitopas	41	55	28	35	3
Ptb 18 ^a	38	65	28	21	-
Tetep	22	58	30	46	5
Lemo	57	-	33	-28	-21
Ptb 21	99	53	-10	-3	-22
Utri Rajapan	100	59	35	5	-39
Khao Mali	80	79	32	47	-16
Khao-Tah-Haeng	100	100	15	28	52
Kirikara	77	96	34	52	20
TN1	84	90	78	65	2

^a Percentage yield reduction was calculated based on the yield of plants inoculated at 60 DAS.

Tetep. The symptoms in plants infected at 30 DAS were milder and those in plants infected at 45 DAS were not clear in any varieties except Kirikara and TN1.

In the first trial, yield reduction was high in plants of almost all varieties infected at 7 or 15 DAS (Table 2). Sitopas, Ptb 18, Tetep, and Lemo have significantly less yield reduction than other varieties infected at the seedling stages. In the second trial, flowering was delayed and yield reduction was less than in the first trial in all varieties. Yield reduction in many varieties inoculated at 30 DAS was higher than in plants inoculated at 7 or 15 DAS. Sitopas, Ptb 18, Lemo, and Ptb 21 had significantly lower yield reduction.

Sitopas, Ptb 18, Lemo, and Tetep developed milder symptoms and sustained less damage when infected with RSV at seedling stage. Their tolerance for RSV was due to their high ability to recover after severe infection at an early stage. □

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Incidence of rice kernel smut (KSm) in Pakistan

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Sixteen rice varieties were evaluated at Gujranwala and Sheikhpura district research farms against KSm by the partial vacuum method using the chlamyospores of *Tilletia barclayana*. Sporidial cultures were prepared on potato dextrose agar for inoculation of 20 panicles of each variety at anthesis. Percentages of infected panicles were recorded at maturity.

Varieties showed differential reaction at both locations. Disease incidence ranged from 5.25 to 95.25% at Sheikhpura and 6.25 to 97.25% at Gujranwala. C622 developed the lowest

Reaction of rice varieties to *Tilletia barclayana*. Islamabad, Pakistan.

Variety	Disease incidence (%)		Reaction
	Sheikhpura	Gujranwala	
Bara, Basmati Pak, Dokri Basmati, Jhona 349, Kangni, Melha 364, Motia, Mushakan, Palman, Ratria, Red rice, Sathra 278	>50	>50	Susceptible
Basmati 370, Sada gulab C622, IR579	>10 <10	>10 <10	Intermediate Resistant

infection, followed by IR579 and Basmati 370 (see table).

None of the varieties appeared to be immune. □

Reaction of selected varieties to tungro (RTV) and green leafhopper (GLH)

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Seven-day-old seedlings of ASD7, ARC11554, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Kataribhog, TKM6, TN1, and Utri Rajapan were individually exposed to one or five RTV-viruliferous adult